

FERROELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF BARIUM TITANATE

Umidjon Sobirjonovich Ismoilov¹

Lutfullo Xayrullo o`g`li Abdulfayizov²

Shukrulla Abdulfayzovich Ermatov³

¹ assistant of department of physics Andijan State University

² student of Andijan State University,

³ docent of department of physics Andijan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6345776>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th February 2022

Accepted: 15th February 2022

Online: 19th February 2022

KEY WORDS

Curie-Weiss temperature, dielectric loss tangent, tetragonal phase

ABSTRACT

The paper presents various physical properties of barium titanate. The ferroelectric properties of this dielectric have been studied. Measurement graphs shown

Barium titanate (BaTiO_3) is a dielectric, the chemical bonds in it are ionic-covalent. It crystallizes into a perovskite structure (Fig. 1), in which each

titanium atom is surrounded by six oxygen atoms, each barium atom by twelve oxygen atoms, and an oxygen atom by two titanium atoms.

Fig.1 TiBaO_3 unit cell (perovskite type)

Oxygen atoms are located at the vertices of regular octahedra, in the center of which are titanium atoms. Sometimes (assuming a predominantly ionic bond), the BaTiO_3 structure is presented as the densest cubic packing formed by O^{2-} and Ba^{2+} ions, with Ti^{4+} ions located in some of its octahedral voids. There are four octahedral and eight

tetrahedral voids per BaTiO_3 unit cell. The Ti^{4+} ion occupies one of the octahedral voids formed by oxygen ions. Barium titanate at room temperature has a polycrystalline perovskite structure. The displacement of Ti, OI, and OII ions along the Z axis by 0.014s, -0.023s, and -0.04s, respectively, is the cause of spontaneous

polarization $P_s \approx 0.25 \text{ C/m}^2$. Figure 2 shows the temperature dependence of ϵ and $\text{tg}\delta$, as well as the course of dependence $1/\epsilon(T)$ and the change in the crystal structure during the thermal transition from the ferroelectric phase to the paraelectric phase. It should be noted that each

structural transition is accompanied by a phase transition at the Curie point $T'_K = 400^\circ\text{C}$. For pure BaTiO_3 , the temperature T_K is 12° lower. The Curie - Weiss constant for barium titanate is $C = 1.2 \cdot 10^5 \text{ K}$, and the value $\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 10^5$ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Temperature dependence of permittivity ϵ and dielectric loss tangent $\text{tg}\delta$ of BaTiO_3 ceramics. T_K - Curie point, T_0 - Curie - Weiss temperature, 2 - rhombic phase, 1 - rhombohedral phase, 3 - tetragonal phase, 4 - cubic phase

The transition to a non-polarized state will occur when it is heated to 400 K, with a change in the lattice parameters (Fig. 3). Each elementary cell has an electric moment, i.e. the centers of gravity of the electric charges of the particles entering the cell do not coincide.

Fig.3 Graph of changes in the parameters of the crystal lattice in various polymorphic structures

TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF PROPERTIES

The interaction of individual cells with each other in a ferroelectric is such that the ordered arrangement of cells with identically directed electric moments is the

most stable. The orientation of the electric moments of many cells in one direction leads to the formation in the crystal of regions or domains that are uniformly polarized.

The total polarization of a ferroelectric in an external field consists of two processes: an increase in the induced

polarization and a change in the specific weight of domains whose spontaneous momentum is oriented in the direction of the external field. The establishment of full polarization in a strong field is a complex process, since in the general case both spontaneous P_{sp} and induced P_{ind} polarization are nonlinear functions of the field strength. In areas where the induced

polarization can be considered a linear function of the field strength, the division of polarizations is carried out as follows: the saturation branch of the hysteresis loop (Fig. 4) is extrapolated to the field value equal to zero, and then the section AB corresponds to the induced, and the section BO corresponds to the spontaneous polarization.

Fig.4 Hysteresis loop

At a certain temperature, spontaneous polarization and the associated hysteresis loop disappear.

Fig.5 Unit cells of four $BaTiO_3$ phases; a - cubic unit cell, stable above 400 K; b - tetragonal, stable in the temperature range 280-400 K; c - rhombic, stable in the temperature range 180-250 K; d - rhombohedral, stable below 180 K. The primes indicate the initial cubic phase.

In the range of 273-295 K, the $BaTiO_3$ cell is tetragonal (Fig. 5 b), at 400 K a phase transition occurs and the tetragonal cell turns into a cubic one, so that at 400 K it is already cubic (Fig. 5,a), and the domains are destroyed due to thermal movement. When cooled to 183 K, the second phase transition is observed for $BaTiO_3$, and the cell turns from tetragonal to rhombic (Fig. 5, c), and at temperatures below 183 K, a phase transition occurs, at which the cell turns into monoclinic or triclinic. (Fig. 5,d)

But these phase transitions do not destroy the domain structure, although the spontaneous polarization vectors change their direction. In a tetragonal cell, which differs slightly from a cubic one, the ratio of the axes $c/a = 1.01$, and the spontaneous polarization vector is directed along the c axis. Below 273 K for a rhombic grating, the spontaneous polarization vector is directed along the diagonal of the unit cell. After the next phase transition, the spontaneous

polarization vector is directed along the bulk diagonal.

In the tetragonal cell of BaTiO₃, the ferroelectric axis is directed along the c axis. The direction perpendicular to it is denoted by a. The permittivity is a tensor,

and for BaTiO₃ the largest changes in the region of phase transitions are observed for the ϵ_a component (Fig. 6). But at the Curie point, ϵ_a and ϵ_c merge, i.e. these components are equal.

Fig.6 Temperature dependence of dielectric permittivity of BaTiO₃, measured in the direction of the ferroelectric axis c and axis perpendicular to it a

This dependence for barium titanate cannot be considered as a typical graph for the components of ϵ tensors in any ferroelectrics. For Rochelle salt, which has two Curie points (at 255 K and 296 K), between which spontaneous polarization is observed, the ferroelectric axis is the a axis of the monoclinic structure. It is only along

this axis that the ferroelectric properties of NaKC₄H₄O₆·4H₂O are revealed. In the direction of the axes b and c, ferroelectric properties do not appear, and the permittivities ϵ_b and ϵ_c are only a few units (Fig. 7).

Fig.7 Dependence of the permittivity a along the ferroelectric axis ϵ_a and permeabilities ϵ_b and ϵ_c along the axes b and c on temperature (a) and the location of these axes (b) in a salt crystal

ϵ also depends on BaTiO₃ impurities (Fig. 8)

Fig.8 Dependence of dielectric constant of barium titanate on additives

The temperature dependence in the non-polar modification or the paraelectric state can be represented by the Curie-Weiss law:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{C}{T - T_k} \quad (1)$$

where ε is the magnetic susceptibility;

C is the Curie constant depending on the substance;

T is the absolute temperature in kelvins;

T_c - Curie temperature, K.

For barium titanate, the absolute values of C vary greatly among different researchers, which is associated with different technologies for obtaining samples. Often take $C = 10^5$ K.

The properties of barium titanate with phase transition 1 (PT1) close to phase transition 2 (PT2) can be described similarly to the properties of ferroelectrics with PT2 using the thermodynamic theory. According to this theory, ferroelectrics with PT1 in the PT temperature range exhibit instability and a dielectric hysteresis loop. The Curie-Weiss law has the same analytical form (1), however, it exhibits features. If for PT2 the transition occurs at $T = T_k$ and $\alpha = 0$, then for PT1 $\alpha \neq 0$.

On fig. 9 shows the temperature dependences of P_s and ε in ferroelectrics with PT1.

Fig.9 Temperature dependence of spontaneous polarization (a) and inverse permittivity (b) in ferroelectrics with PT2. T'_k - Curie point, T_k - Curie - Weiss temperature
The Curie point characterizes the phase transition temperature of ferroelectrics of

the 1st kind. The Curie - Weiss temperature, $T_0 = T_k$, shows the temperature shift of PT1 compared to PT2.

CONCLUSION

During the analysis of the study of various authors, it turned out that barium titanate is an unusual ferroelectric, since it has properties that are characteristic only of it. In particular, of greatest interest is its large dielectric constant. And along with the desire of mankind to make all means, in particular, communications, as easy and small as possible, its characteristics as the basis for semiconductor devices are of particular interest to mankind. Therefore, it was relevant to study it at the micro - and even nano - levels.

Scientists from different countries, starting from the very moment of the discovery of this substance, have been conducting intensive research to identify the presence of various properties. These

studies made it possible to distinguish this ferroelectric into a special class. Since he made a mini-revolution in the field of dielectrics. The reason for this was the presence of a large coefficient of dielectric constant (10 times) than that of previously known substances. Also, the peculiar dependence of the dielectric constant on various factors (temperature, impurities, frequency, intensity) indicates that its polarization has some features. For example, $BaTiO_3$ has the highest Curie temperature among other ferroelectrics. Such features, as well as the simplicity of the crystal lattice and the easy method of obtaining, by simple firing, open up many prospects for its application in technology. And these perspectives are already applied. In the future, this connection is still waiting for its significant application in the booming computer industry.

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